

A Study on Smartphone Addiction among Student Teachers of B.Ed.

R. Manikandan¹, Dr. K. Prema²

¹ Ph.D., Research Scholar, Department of Education, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore.

² Assistant Professor, Department of Education (SDE), Bharathiar University, Coimbatore.

Corresponding author- R. Manikandan

Email- manim.ed.98765@gmail.com

Abstract

The aim of the study was to find out the significant difference in smart phone addiction among student teachers in B.Ed. The survey method was used for this investigation. The sample consists of 100 student teachers in the Coimbatore district. A random sampling technique was used. Smartphone addiction scale among student teachers was developed by the investigator and used to collect the data. The statistical techniques used were mean, standard deviation, 't' and F tests. The findings of the study were: i) There is a significant difference between male and female student teachers in their smart phone addiction. ii) There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their smart phone addiction.

Key Words: Smartphone addiction, Smartphone usage, Student teachers.

Introduction:

According to data details provided by Simon Kemp among Digital India, There were 692.0 million internet users in India at the start of 2023, when internet penetration stood at 48.7 %, In January 2023, India had 467.0 million social media users, alongside 32.8% of the entire population. In early 2023, 1.10 billion cellular mobile connections were active in India, which represents 77.0% of the total population. In the beginning of 2023, India had 692.0 million internet users. At the very start of 2023, India's internet penetration rate was 48.7 % of the overall population. In the first quarter of 2023, there were 467.0 million social media users in India. At the start of 2023, the number of social media users in India was equivalent to 32.8 % of the population in its entirety. Meanwhile, data provided through the ad planning tools of key social media platforms reveals that 398.0 million users aged 18 and above were using social media in India at the start of 2023, which represented 40.2 % of the total population aged 18 and over at that point in time. Today the world is travelling in the 21st century with the help of technology. While man is progressing in various evolutions, technology is also growing in various dimensions. Now a day, the use of gadgets and the help of technology in anything and everything is widespread worldwide. Various machines and inventions abound in human evolution. In the past, human communication was only expressed through direct speech, gestures, and body language. But in today's era, with the help of smart phone technology, we can do countless activities such as instant conversation with other people, video face to face conversation, money transfer etc. In today's era the need for communication technology is increasing day by day. This change is one of the requirements of change. Previously the two technologies were separate categories. There was also cell phone and internet. But due to various technological developments, in

today's era both the internet and Smartphone have been merged into one unit and it has changed into smart phone. Here also various facilities related to job related information, entertainment and games are available in the Smartphone. These changes have created various impacts and developments in all countries of the world.

A smart phone is an indispensable device in everyone's hands today. The previous money exchange system was a bit less. The reason is that the human attitude has changed with today's digital payment system. Especially the Internet service on smart phones is developing in different stages according to need. For example, the advancement of internet service from 2G to 5G. While this massive 2G to 5G evolution brings many benefits, it also brings many disadvantages. Especially in the education of today's young generation, it causes some problems in various activities. Especially among adolescents, like school students and college students, due to the use of smart phones, they suffer academic setbacks and subsequent psychological problems.

Effects of Smart Phone Addiction:

Costly:

Despite the fact that there are several smart phones available at different budgets, high-end phones with outstanding hardware and features can be expensive. Some apps won't be completely running because we have to purchase them to utilize all of their features and functionality. Moreover, we must maintain an Internet plan if our plan is to use a phone to access the Internet.

Distracting:

Smartphone's are among the most distracting gadgets today. While working on a crucial task, you may be interrupted by applications that alert you to changes, messages, the newest products, and other things. Smartphone use while walking, learning, conversing with people, working, eating, and sometimes while driving might reduce

attention.

Addiction:

One of the most hazardous impacts of using a smart phone is addiction, which occurs when you use it first thing in the morning each day before doing anything else. As a result, you run the risk of causing "nomophobia." A smart phone addict is unable to quit using their phone. Increases in risky health conditions like Angry, sadness, anxiety, and irritability are brought on by mobile phone addiction.

Waste of time:

Mobile phones are the biggest waste of time. even though they have many advantages for users. Smartphone's mostly affect teenagers and students because they use their phones more for enjoyment than for learning, preferring to play video games, listen to music, and engage in other forms of entertainment. They consequently waste their valuable time on the phone.

Sensor videos:

Despite the fact that the Internet has many advantages for people, accessing the internet and information is usually challenging. Because children or even adults may see pornographic, violent, or other unreliable information, whether with intention or not. If have children, must limit their use of devices.

Threats to privacy:

Even if they are made private, security concerns and vulnerabilities are present on smart phones constantly. Hackers and several virus strains are both readily available. Hackers are individuals that attempt to obtain your personal information illegally, and viruses are powerful, virtual threats designed to wipe out the data on your smart phone. Smartphone's are exposed to these threats when you access and browse the Internet. Therefore, be aware that the URL you are opening is secure.

Health Issues:

One of the dangerous drawbacks of smart phones is that they have a detrimental effect on health and result in numerous health issues due to the HEV light they emit. For instance, if use your phone a lot, especially late at night, it may be the source of your or another eye's concerns with edoema. Additionally, the radiofrequency energy that the smart phone emits might be absorbed by the body's tissues. A late night's sleep might also have negative effects on health. sleep less than necessary, which is another typical negative impact of smart phone use.

Distance from family:

The main drawback of smart phones today is the lack of social interaction due to their distance from family members. Because they are so engaged in their electronics, they can no longer maintain a two-minute conversation with the person seated next

to them. Instead, they engage in conversations with a seatmate thousands of miles away. For instance, those at home dining spend time on their phones; four friends sitting next to one another choose to converse on their phones rather than interact with one another; etc.

Cell phone Driving:

People are now so accustomed to using smart phones. Some people even use them to communicate while driving. Consistent mobile use significantly exacerbates this fault or harm.

Need and Significance of the Study:

Nowadays ICT (information and communication technology) has expanded at an astonishing rate. The smart phone is one of the most important information and communication devices, and its popularity has skyrocketed in recent years. It has turned into a vital source of information and entertainment for students. It has enabled students to interact with and learn from teachers and students from all around the world. It is really productive while students use their smart phones in a beneficial way. Students right now depend on social networking sites like WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Twitter via their smart phones. Although the fact that electronic devices have given students novel ways to socialize and interact with, it has fewer face-to-face communication among students, friends, and family members. The Smartphone's accessibility to an extensive variety of information affects students' intellectual competence, innovation, and ethical values. In addition, students who spend more time on their smart phones playing games and chatting affect other psychological problems. In general, consistent smart phone use leads to an addiction to them among students who use them.

According to psychological research, students use their smart phones excessively to compensate for sociological or psychological obstacles, as well as inadequacies in personal well-being in everyday offline lives. Overuse of the smart phone has been associated with sensation-seeking (the want for excitement and sensory pleasure), loneliness, and emotional disorders (such as depression and Loneliness) (Mehroof & Griffiths, 2010, as quoted in Smahel et al., 2012). According to Yang and Tung's (2007) study, students with psychological illnesses such as dependence, depression, excessive Sleep disturbance, were more inclined to get addicted to the smart phone. As a consequence, the researcher thought it is essential to investigate the association between smart phone addiction and psychological problems such as OCD, FOMO, Sleep Disturbance, loneliness, stress amongst student teachers.

Statement of the Problem:

Smart phones are the most crucial technological gadget in the world, Smartphone addiction has grown into a problem among students as the use of smart phones develops drastically each year. Because of their psychological impairment, some students spend more time on their smart phones playing online games, chatting, watching videos, or simply listening to music. A number of studies have shown that an addiction to smart phones is related to some psychological problems (Kim et al., 2006; Yen et al., 2008; Kim & Haridakis, 2009; Robu & Tcaciuc, 2010; Sepehrian & Jokar, 2013), and the researchers strongly believed in psychological problems such as OCD, FoMo, Sleep disturbance, loneliness, stress, and becoming addicted to the smartphone. Solving the aforementioned psychological problems might help them overcome their smart phone addiction. In the past, most studies on smart phone addiction were primarily focused with one or two psychological variables, and such studies on smart phone addiction have been identified in many different nations such as western countries, Korea, Hong Kong, Singapore, and so on. However, this study in India is quite small, and the levels of smart phone addiction among student -teachers remain unreliable. As a result, the investigator selected the title and stipulated the problem of the study as "**A STUDY ON SMART PHONE Addiction among Student Teachers of B.Ed.**"

Operational Definitions of Key Terms:

Smartphone Addiction:

In the current study, smart phone addiction is defined as excessive, frequent use of a smart phone that leads to psychological, social, physical, and academic problems in the life of the user.

Student-Teacher:

Student teachers who are doing B.Ed courses in B.Ed Colleges.

Objective of the Study:

1. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the mean score of smartphone addiction among student teachers with respect to gender.
2. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the mean score of smartphone addiction among student teachers with respect to Locality.
3. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the mean score of smartphone addiction among student teachers with respect to Pedagogy subject in B.Ed.
4. To find out whether there is any significant in the mean score of smart phoneaddiction among student teachers with respect to medium of instruction.

To find out whether there is any significant in the

mean score of smart phoneaddiction among student teachers with respect to types of family.

Hypotheses of the Study:

1. There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction amongst student teachers with respect to gender.
2. There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction amongst student teachers with respect to Locality.
3. There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction amongst student teachers with respect to the Pedagogy subject in B.Ed.
4. There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction amongst student teachers with respect to medium of instruction.
5. There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction amongst student teachers with respect to types of family.

Review of Literature:

Kalaivani A/P Munusamy(2022),Effects of Mobile Phone Usage Behavior and Mobile Phone Addiction among Youth. Aim of the study: To investigate one of the significant areas of mobile phone usage to analyze the psychological context and the relationships for young users between mobile phone addiction and mobile phone usage. Methods & Sample of the study: The research was carried out on 400 youths in Klang Valley using the survey method. Finding of the study: youths mobile phone usage behavior and addiction in moderate level. A serious attention must be given to this issue before the youths become highly addicted..

Naveenta Gupta,et.al(2015),Pattern of mobile phone usage and its effects on psychological health, sleep, and academic performance in students of a medical university. Aims and Objective: This study was designed to assess the mobile phone usage pattern and its negative effects on psychological health, sleep, and academic performance in students of a medical university. Materials and Methods: A descriptive study was conducted on a total of 1,000 medical students aged between 17 and 24 years who were using mobile phone for at least 1 year. Tool: They were requested to fill a specially designed, self-administrated, pretested, questionnaire that comprised details of their frequency and pattern of using mobile phone and its effects on their psychological health, sleep-related behavioral issues, and academic performance. The data collected were statistically analyzed. Besides the positive role of mobile phones in our daily lives, its overuse presents negative impact on psychological health, sleep, and academic performance of students.

Navya Gangadaran(2022),Mobile Phone Addiction as an Emerging Behavioral Form of Addiction Among Adolescents in India. Aim of the

study: To determine the prevalence of mobile phone addiction among adolescents and its associated risk factors among adolescents. Method and results: A community-based, cross-sectional study was conducted among 264 adolescents (10-19 years) of low-income urban areas of Delhi. The prevalence of mobile phone addiction in the participants was 33.0% (95% CI: 27.2-38.6). The addiction was higher among boys (33.6%) than girls (32.3%) (p=0.835). Mobile phone addiction was found to be significantly higher among those adolescents who had ≥ 3 siblings, those belonging to nuclear families, and among late-onset users (≥ 16 years). Late-onset users (adjusted odds ratio {aOR}: 3.398; 95% CI: 1.307-8.833) and ≥ 3 siblings (aOR: 1.980; 95% CI: 1.141-3.437) were independent predictors of mobile phone addiction. The mean time spent on mobile phones was significantly higher among those with addiction but no significant gender difference was found between time spent on phones and addiction. Conclusion: The high prevalence of mobile phone addiction found in our study is an indication of the potential public health concern posed by mobile phone use among adolescents in urban settings. Hence, it is essential to limit the access to mobile phones for important utility purposes for adolescents

Renuka K (2019), Prevalence of smart phone addiction in an urban area of Kanchipuram district, Tamil Nadu: a cross sectional study. Aim of the study: To find out the prevalence of smartphone addiction in the study area. Methods: Community based cross sectional study carried out in Anakaputhur, Tamil Nadu from November 2018 to January 2019. Sample: Sample size of 400 was calculated using the formula $4PQ/L2$. The respondents were selected by systematic random sampling. Subjects 18 years and above who are using mobile phones were included in the study. Data Analysis: analyzed using SPSS 16 version and presented using descriptive and analytical statistics. Results: Out of 405 participants 191 participants were non smart phone users and 214 were smart phone users. Overall prevalence of smart phone addiction was 27.6%. Male respondents were more addicted than the female (OR-1.94, 95%CI: 1.12-

3.77, p=0.01). There was a statistically significant association between subjects <45 years of age and smart phone addiction (OR-2.33, 95% CI: 1.31-4.13, p=0.003) compared to older age group. Conclusion: prevalence of smart phone addiction is high that has to be addressed seriously. This can be tackled by better lifestyle modification, awareness creation and attitudinal changes..

**Research Methodology:
 Population of the study:**

The main purpose of survey research is to describe the characteristics of a population. This is usually accomplished by collecting data from a sample. Therefore, the first step in Sampling is used to define the population. In this study, all the student teachers who are studying B.Ed., (Bachelor of Education) at the college of education in Coimbatore district have been taken as the population for the study. The student teacher had taken the population, particularly in the Coimbatore district.

Sample selected for the study:

A random sampling method was adopted to choose the sample in the present study. Random sampling is a way of selecting a sample of observations from a population in order to make inferences about the population. A simple random sample means that every case in the population has an equal probability of inclusion in the sample. 100 student teachers were selected as the sample from two colleges of education, Coimbatore district.

Tools for the present study:

In 1951, Lee cronbach's developed Alpha to provide a measure of the internal Consistency of a test or scale. Internal consistency describes the extent to which all items in a test measure the same concept or construct and hence it is connected to the interrelatedness of the items with in the test. A rating scale is a set of categories designed to elicit information about a quantitative or a qualitative attribute. Here, the respondent is asked to indicate a degree of agreement and disagreement with each of a series of statement. Each scale item has 5 response categories ranging from strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree. It is a five-point scale ranging from the value 1 to 5.

Tool	Number of items	Cronbach's alpha
Smartphone Addiction	20	0.786

From the above table, it is shown that Cronbach's alpha is 0.786, which indicates an average level of internal consistency of the tool.

Delimitation of the Study:

Research studies in general will have limitations due to many factors. The following limitations were

unavoidable in the present study.

1. The study has been conducted on a sample of student teachers.
2. The study has been conducted only in Coimbatore district.

Data Analysis:

Table 1:

There is a significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction among studentteachers with respect to gender.

Gender	N	Mean	Std	t-value	Remarks
Male	26	160.18	36.346	2.326	Significant
Female	74	198.07	74.790		

In the above table-1 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 2.326 greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is

significant difference between male and female teacher educators in their smart phone addiction. Female student teacher have better than mean value male studentteacher.

Table 2:

There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction among studentteachers with respect to Locality.

Locality	N	Mean	Std	t-value	Remarks
Rural	50	196.78	72.490	0.711	Not Significant
Urban	50	182.67	67.515		

In the above table-2 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 0.711 lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is no

significant difference between rural and urban student teacher in their smart phone addiction. Rural student teacher have better than mean value urban student teacher .

Table 3:

There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction among studentteachers with respect to the Pedagogy subject in B.Ed.

Pedagogy subject in B.Ed.	N	Mean	Std	t-value	Remarks
Arts	44	181.13	68.970	0.410	Not Significant
Science	56	193.33	71.305		

In the above table-3 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 0.410 lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is

no significant difference between arts and science student teachers in their smart phone addiction. Science student teacher have better than mean value arts student teacher.

Table 4:

There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction among studentteachers with respect to medium of instruction.

Medium of instruction	N	Mean	Std	t-value	Remarks
Tamil	44	186.34	66.307	0.392	Not Significant
English	56	194.38	75.531		

In the above table-4 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 0.392 lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is significant difference between Tamil medium and

English medium student teachers in their smart phone addiction. English medium student teachers have better than mean value Tamil medium student teachers.

Table 5:

There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction among studentteachers with respect to family.

Family	N	Mean	Std	t-value	Remarks
Joint	35	185.08	63.009	0.355	Not Significant
Nuclear	65	192.15	73.735		

In the above table-5 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 0.355 lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is

rejected. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is no significant difference between joint family and nuclear family student teachers in their smart phone

addiction. Nuclear family student teachers have better than mean value joint family student teachers.

Findings:

1. There is a significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction among student teachers with respect to gender.
2. There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction among student teachers with respect to Locality.
3. There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction among student teachers with respect to the Pedagogy subject in B.Ed.
4. There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction among student teachers with respect to medium of instruction.
5. There is no significant difference in the means score of smart phone addiction among student teachers with respect to types of family.

Conclusion:

To conclude, the high significant of smart phone addiction found in female student teachers. Female student teachers who are at a transition stage are at a higher risk for technological dependence and addictions nowadays. Hence, it is essential to limit the access to smart phone for important utility purposes to student teacher of female. Smart phone addiction impacts people of all ages, notably students, workers, businesspeople, and homemakers. The vast majority of college students are easy affects for smart phone addiction. It has a negative effect on their psychologically, making it worse. So pursuing student teachers should know the psychological effects of smart phone addiction to protect them from their own smart phone addiction. The person responsible for a good day is the teacher. Even though their major role is making the students for modern world with discipline, self control and balance when using smart phone gadgets. Providing peer group relationship, real life social support, promotion of self-control and building intrapersonal skills will stimulate the spirit of enthusiasm and at the same time, can lead the students to achieve great things in their life.

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